

Effectiveness of Interactive Simulation-Based Instruction and Video-Assisted Instruction on Students' Performance in Radioactivity Concept in Port Harcourt, Rivers State, Nigeria

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Abstract

This study investigated the effect of interactive simulation-based instruction and video-assisted instruction on students' performance in the concept of Radioactivity in Port Harcourt, Rivers State. The quasi-experimental pre-test, post-test, non-randomized control group design was adopted for the study. The study was guided by three objectives, three research questions, and three hypotheses. A sample size of 133 Senior Secondary School 3 Physics students from two public co-educational secondary schools was involved in the study. The Simple random sampling technique was used to select two schools. The Simple random sampling technique was also used to select an intact class from each of the two schools. The research instrument used for data collection was a validated researcher-constructed instrument titled Radioactivity Performance Test. A reliability coefficient of 0.99 was obtained for the instrument using the Kuder-Richardson 21 formula. Mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions, while Analysis of Covariance and Partial Eta squared were used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The findings of the study revealed that the Interactive Simulation-based Instruction enhanced students' performance more than Video-Assisted Instruction, and the male students significantly performed better than the female students. The interaction of instructional strategy and gender was however, not significant on the performance of students in Radioactivity concept. It was therefore recommended that Physics teachers should blend Interactive Simulation-based Instruction and Video-Assisted Instruction with the conventional teaching methods when teaching difficult and abstract Physics concepts such as Radioactivity.

Keywords: *Interactive Simulation-Based Instruction, Video-Assisted Instruction, Performance, Radioactivity, Physics.*

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Introduction

Science education, as defined by Nwanekezi and Arokoyu (2016) is the study of interrelationships between science as a discipline and the application of educational principles to its understanding. A strong foundation in science education can amplify the voice of a nation such as Nigeria on the global stage through critical thinking and advancement in technology. One essential subject in science education is Physics. Physics plays a crucial role in technological development, acting as an underlying foundation for so many innovations and inventions. Physics laws and principles govern the behavior of matter, energy, and the universe. Physics can be seen as the mother of engineering and technological advancement. For example, the understanding of mechanics, material science, and thermodynamics in Physics helps in mechanical engineering, while electrical engineering must have knowledge of the principles of electromagnetism, electricity, and electronics. Physics is thus the bedrock of technological development (Busari, Gana, Gimba, & Salako, 2022). Unfortunately, the study by Bello et al. (2018) revealed that half of the topics in Physics are difficult. This difficulty in Physics topics undeniably leads to students' poor performance in Physics. Ndioho, Ndioho and Akpan (2022) also reported some challenging topics in Physics, and recommended the use of simulation to teach such concepts.

Performance is the mark attained in a given test when measured in comparison with other students. To this end, performance can be seen as the degree of good, average and poor when a test is conducted by a teacher for students and placed on a scale for evaluation or placement. High performance in students can be achieved if an effective teaching strategy is used by a teacher. Teaching strategy is a clear path toward improving students' learning quality (Ogegbo & Ramnarain, 2022). Physics teachers need to embrace the use of dynamic, effective, participatory, and interactive strategies to meet the current trend and time. Obomanu, Nwanekezi and Morah (2019) advocated for the use of hands-on activities. This may however not be appropriate, nor effective for all topics in Physics due to the complexities involved in some topics and the danger some topics can cause in the laboratory, such topic is radioactivity. To this end, the use of modern teaching strategies should be adopted. Such teaching strategies include interactive simulation-based instruction and video-assisted instruction.

Interactive simulation-based instruction refers to the imitation of an ideal system for students to interact with (Fok, 2017). Interactive simulation-based instruction is bringing the real world, which originally may or may not be possible to interact with in an ideal case. This may be due to the complexity, abstract nature, difficult nature, or volatile nature of the concepts to be learnt. Interactive simulation-based instruction also comes in handy when the needed materials for the lesson are either not available or are costly to procure. With the use of Interactive simulation-based instruction, students have the opportunity to interact and learn without encountering any danger. Video-Assisted Instruction is the use of videos to bring about learning, giving the learners a better learning opportunity in terms of audio and visual interpretation of the concept. The videos are usually short clips focusing on a particular topic or concept.

As the name is, Video-Assisted Instruction may yield better results in a lesson, when video is incorporated into the lesson to assist learning on a particular concept.

Interactive simulation-based instruction is a technology-based instructional strategy that has great potential in the study of scientific concepts. Ogegbo and Ramnarain (2022) found that Interactive Simulation Technology enhanced Grade 11 physical sciences learners' conceptual understanding of electrostatics concept in Physics. Ozcan et al. (2020) found that the 6th-grade students taught the concept of gas kinetic theory using PhET simulation-based instruction, had a greater achievement than those taught using laboratory kit activities. Arifin et al. (2022) similarly found that students' mathematical grasp of fractions was greatly enhanced through PhET Interactive Simulation. Najib et al. (2022), in the same vein, found that PhET interactive simulation activities significantly enhanced secondary school students' Physics achievement. Akpan and Obafemi (2023) also found that students taught quadratic graphs using PhET Manipulative Instruction, which is a form of Virtual Manipulative Instruction, performed significantly higher than those taught using Concrete Manipulative Instruction. Jack and Gamnjoh (2020) found that Computer Simulation enhanced the performance of students taught Acid-base reactions more than the conventional method. Ojo (2020) similarly found that the pupils taught using the Computer simulation strategy performed significantly better in Basic Science than pupils taught using the conventional strategy. In the same vein, Omoniyi (2021) found a significant difference in performance among students taught electrolysis using Computer Simulation Instruction, Four mode Application Technique, and Lecture method, in favour of students taught electrolysis using Computer Simulation Instruction. Macaulay and Obafemi (2022) also found that the simulation instructional strategy significantly enhanced students' performance in the Electrolysis concept than the Teacher demonstration method. Kaysi (2025) found that the use of simulation software by university students resulted in a significant improvement in their achievement. Ndukwe and Obafemi (2023), however, found a significant difference between the effects of the guided-inquiry method and virtual laboratories, in favour of guided-discovery method.

Video-Assisted Instruction has also been found to have potential in teaching and learning. Abragan and Hambre (2017) found that video-assisted instruction enhanced Grade 6 pupils' performance in science and Health more than the lecture method. Khan (2019) similarly found that video-based instruction improved the academic performance of the students in Biology more than the conventional method of teaching. Grustan and Buniel (2022), in the same vein, found that lecture-demo video enhanced students' performance, and that enabled a positive learning outcome in learners' competency mastery of Electrical installation and maintenance. Entice and Comahig (2023) found that students taught mathematics using Video Assisted Instruction had a better performance than the students taught using Modular Assisted Instruction. George and Kakraba (2023) similarly found that undergraduate students who were taught geometry with the help of videos performed better than those who were taught geometry with diagrams, while Panolino and Ambayon (2024) found that the instructional video material with the integration of visual, auditory, and kinesthetic learning style significantly enhanced students' performance in English.

Investigating the influence of gender on the performance of students in scientific concepts, Obafemi and Aderonmu (2020) discovered that the male students significantly performed better than the female students in Physics. Obafemi and Rowland (2022) found that the male students performed slightly better than female

students in Sound energy, though the difference in their performance was not significant. Ndukwe and Obafemi (2023) similarly found that though the male students performed better than the female students, the difference in their performance in Redox reaction concept was not significant. In the same vein, Obafemi and Ogbu (2025) found that though the male students performed better than the female students, the difference in their performance was not found to be statistically significant. On the contrary, Chibabi et al. (2018) found that the female students performed significantly higher than the male students in Biology. Okwara et al. (2019) reported that female students performed better than the male students in Basic Science, though the difference in their performance was not statistically significant, while Akpan and Obafemi (2023) discovered that, though female students had a higher performance than male students in quadratic graphs, the difference in their performance was not statistically significant.

Investigating the interaction of instructional strategy and gender on students' performance, Ugwu and Diovu (2016) found no significant interaction of instructional strategy and gender on the academic achievement of students when indigenous knowledge and practices were integrated into Chemistry. Abumchukwu et al. (2021) similarly found no significant interaction of instructional strategy and gender on students' performance in Chemistry. Macaulay and Obafemi (2022), in the same vein, found no significant joint effect of gender and instructional strategy on the performance of students in the concept of Electrolysis. Obafemi and Rowland (2022) discovered no significant joint effect of gender and instructional strategy on the performance of students in the concept of Sound energy. Ndukwe and Obafemi (2023) similarly, found no significant interaction of instructional strategy and gender on students' performance in Redox reaction. Obafemi and Ogbu (2025) also found that the interaction of instructional method and gender on students' academic performance in oscillatory motion was not statistically significant. On the contrary, Ugwu (2014) found a significant interaction of strategy and gender on students' performance in Basic science. Obafemi (2015) similarly discovered a significant joint effect of strategy and gender on students' performance at the application level of students' performance in the concept of Light waves, while Ibeneme and Akinlabi (2021) discovered a significant interaction of strategy and gender on the performance of students in Instruction on Block laying.

Statement of the Problem

As reported by Onwioduokit (1996) and Adebisi et al. (2020), Radioactivity concept is one of the difficult concepts in Physics. It is not only difficult but also abstract in nature. The West African Examination Council (WAEC) Chief Examiner reported that in the year 2019 WASSCE Physics Examination, students manifested weakness in questions set on Radioactivity. Also in the years 2020 and 2021 WASSCE Physics Examinations, questions on Radioactivity were attempted by very few candidates who could not correctly answer the questions, leading to poor performance in the questions on Radioactivity concept. It was consequently recommended by the WAEC Chief Examiner that Physics teachers upgrade their teaching skills to embrace modern technology. Could the avoidance of the questions by the candidates be because they did not understand the concept due to ineffective instructional strategies? Could the use of technology-based strategies such as the Interactive Simulation-Based Instruction and Video-Assisted Instruction, enhance students' performance in Radioactivity concept? This study therefore, investigated the effect of Interactive

Simulation-Based Instruction and Video-Assisted Instruction on students' performance in Radioactivity concept in Port Harcourt, Rivers State.

Aim and Objectives of the Study

The aim of this study was to investigate the effect of Interactive Simulation-Based Instruction and Video-Assisted Instruction on students' performance in Radioactivity concept in Port Harcourt, Rivers State. The specific objectives of this study were to:

1. investigate the difference between the performance of students taught using Interactive Simulation-based Instruction, and those taught using Video-Assisted Instruction in radioactivity concept.
2. ascertain the difference between the performance of male and female students in radioactivity concept.
3. determine the joint effect of instructional strategy and gender on students' performance in radioactivity concept.

Research Questions

The following question guided the study:

1. What is the difference between the performance of students taught using Interactive Simulation-based Instruction and those taught using Video-Assisted Instruction in radioactivity concept?
2. What difference exists between the performance of male and female students in radioactivity concept?
3. What is the joint effect of instructional strategy and gender on students' performance in radioactivity concept?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses will be tested at 0.05 probability level:

1. There is no significant difference between the performance of students taught using Interactive Simulation-based Instruction, and those taught using Video-Assisted Instruction in Radioactivity concept.
2. There is no significant difference between the performance of male and female students in radioactivity concept.
3. There is no significant joint effect of instructional strategy and gender on the performance of students in radioactivity concept.

Materials and Methods

This study investigated the effect of Interactive Simulation-Based Instruction and Video-Assisted Instruction on students' performance in Radioactivity concept in Port Harcourt, Rivers State. The study adopted the quasi-experimental non-randomized pre-test and post-test design. The population for the study comprises all Senior Secondary School 3 (SS3), which was 5,168 (five thousand, one hundred and sixty eight) students. The sample for this study was made up of 133 (one hundred and thirty-three) students from two co-educational senior secondary schools. The simple random sampling technique was then used in selecting two public co-educational schools. One intact class was also randomly selected in each of the two schools. One intact class was

assigned the experimental group while the second intact class was assigned the control group. The research instrument was a performance test titled 'Radioactivity Performance Test' (RPT). The instrument was made up of two sections. Section A was used to obtain the bio-data of the students, while Section B contained 50 multiple-choice questions to measure students' performance in the concept of Radioactivity. Each correct answer attracted 1 mark, totaling up to a maximum of 50 marks. The instrument was validated by two Physics teachers who have taught Physics for a decade and experts in measurement and evaluation to establish the face, content, and construct validities of the research instrument. The reliability coefficient of 0.99 was obtained for the instrument (RPT) using the Kuder-Richardson 21 formula.

The instrument (RPT) was administered to each of the intact groups as the pre-treatment test (pre-test). Thereafter, the experimental group was taught the Physics concept of Radioactivity using the Interactive Simulation-based Instruction, while the control group was taught the same concept of Radioactivity using Video-Assisted Instruction. After the teaching, the instrument (RPT) was re-administered to each of the intact groups as the post-treatment test (post-test). The answers provided by the students to the pre-test and post-test were graded, and the scores on the pre-test and post-test constituted the data for this study. For the data analysis, the research questions were answered using Mean and standard deviation, while the hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance using Analysis of Covariance and Partial Eta Squared.

Results

Research Questions

Research Question 1: What is the difference between the performance of students taught using Interactive Simulation-based Instruction and those taught using Video-Assisted Instruction in radioactivity concept?

Table 1. Mean and Standard Deviation Values of Students' Performance Classified by Instructional Strategy

Strategy		Pretest	Posttest	Gain
Interactive Simulation-Based	Mean	12.7288	23.0508	10.3220
	Std. Deviation	6.7717	8.2971	7.9815
	N	59	59	59
Video-Assisted Instruction	Mean	10.0811	19.9054	9.8243
	Std. Deviation	4.6072	6.7034	8.1700
	N	74	74	74

Table 1 shows that the students taught using Interactive Simulation-based Instruction had a mean gain of 10.32 and standard deviation of 7.98 ($M_g = 10.32$, $SD = 7.98$), while the students taught using Video-Assisted Instruction had a mean gain of 9.82 and standard deviation of 8.17 ($M_g = 9.82$, $SD = 8.17$). These results show that the students taught using Interactive Simulation-based Instruction had a better performance than the students taught using Video-Assisted Instruction. This indicates that Interactive Simulation-based Instruction enhanced students' performance more than Video-Assisted Instruction.

Research Question 2: What difference exist between the performance of male and female students in Radioactivity concept?

Table 2. Mean and Standard Deviation Values of Students' Performance Classified by Gender

Gender		Pretest	Posttest	Gain
Male	Mean	14.4194	25.4194	11.0000
	Std. Deviation	6.4847	9.1279	7.8188
	N	31	31	31
Female	Mean	10.2941	20.0490	9.7549
	Std. Deviation	5.2400	6.6099	8.1477
	N	102	102	102

Table 2 shows that the male students had a mean gain of 11.00 and standard deviation of 7.82 ($Mg = 11.00$, $SD = 7.82$), while the female students had a mean gain of 9.75 and standard deviation of 8.15 ($Mg = 9.75$, $SD = 8.15$). These results show that the male students performed better than the female students.

Research Question 3: What is the joint effect of Instructional strategy and gender on students' performance in Radioactivity concept?

Table 3. Mean and Standard Deviation Values of Students' Performance Classified by Instructional Strategy and Gender

Strategy	Gender		Pretest	Posttest	Gain
Interactive Simulation-Based	Male	Mean	15.2500	26.3333	11.0833
		Std. Deviation	6.7583	9.1446	7.6608
		N	24	24	24
	Female	Mean	11.0000	20.8000	9.8000
		Std. Deviation	6.3059	6.9316	8.2633
		N	35	35	35
Video-Assisted Instruction	Male	Mean	11.5714	22.2857	10.7143
		Std. Deviation	4.7909	9.0132	8.9762
		N	7	7	7
	Female	Mean	9.9254	19.6567	9.7313
		Std. Deviation	4.5968	6.4539	8.1493
		N	67	67	67

Table 3 shows that the male students taught using Interactive Simulation-based Instruction had the highest mean gain of 11.08 and standard deviation of 7.66 ($Mg = 11.08$, $SD = 7.66$), followed by the male students taught using Video-Assisted Instruction with a mean gain of 10.71 and standard deviation of 8.98 ($Mg = 10.71$, $SD = 8.98$), while the female students taught using Video-Assisted Instruction had the least mean gain of 9.73 and standard deviation of 8.15 ($Mg = 9.73$, $SD = 8.15$). This result indicates that the male students taught using Interactive Simulation-based Instruction had the best performance, followed by the male students taught using Video Assisted Instruction, while the female students taught using Video-Assisted Instruction had the least performance in Radioactivity concept.

Hypotheses

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant difference between the performance of students taught using Interactive Simulation-based Instruction, and those taught using Video-Assisted Instruction in Radioactivity concept.

Table 4. Summary of Analysis of Covariance of Students' Performance Classified by Instructional Strategy Using Pretest as Covariate

Tests of Between-Subjects Effects						
Dependent Variable: Posttest						
Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared
Corrected Model	829.387 ^a	2	414.694	7.965	0.001	0.109
Intercept	7977.487	1	7977.487	153.219	0.000	0.541
Pretest	504.602	1	504.602	9.692	0.002	0.069
Strategy	154.602	1	154.602	2.969	0.087	0.022
Error	6768.583	130	52.066			
Total	67943.000	133				
Corrected Total	7597.970	132				

a. R Squared = 0.109 (Adjusted R Squared = 0.095)

Table 4 reveals a value of $F_{1,130} = 2.969$, $p = 0.087$ ($p > 0.05$), partial eta squared = 0.022 for the effect of Instructional Strategy on students' performance in Radioactivity concept. The null hypothesis is therefore retained. This indicates that there is no significant difference between the performance of students taught using Interactive Simulation-based Instruction, and those taught using Video-Assisted Instruction in Radioactivity concept. The partial eta squared value shows that instructional strategy had a small effect on students' performance in Radioactivity concept.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant difference between the performance of male and female students in Radioactivity concept.

Table 5. Summary of Analysis of Covariance of Students' Performance Classified by Gender Using Pretest as Covariate

Tests of Between-Subjects Effects						
Dependent Variable: Posttest						
Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared
Corrected Model	1044.998 ^a	2	522.499	10.366	0.000	0.138
Intercept	7501.619	1	7501.619	148.820	0.000	0.534
Pretest	359.331	1	359.331	7.129	0.009	0.052
Gender	370.213	1	370.213	7.344	0.008	0.053
Error	6552.972	130	50.407			
Total	67943.000	133				
Corrected Total	7597.970	132				

a. R Squared = 0.138 (Adjusted R Squared = 0.124)

Table 5 reveals a value of $F_{1,130} = 7.344$, $p = 0.008$ ($p < 0.05$), partial eta squared = 0.053 for the effect of gender on students' performance in Radioactivity concept. The null hypothesis is therefore rejected. This indicates that there is a significant difference between the performance of male and female students in Radioactivity concept. The

partial eta squared value shows that gender had a small effect on students' performance in Radioactivity concept.

Table 6. Least Significant Difference Post Hoc Analysis of Students' Performance Classified by Gender

Pairwise Comparisons						
Dependent Variable: Posttest						
(I) Gender	(J) Gender	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig. ^b	95% Confidence Interval for Difference ^b	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Male	Female	4.139*	1.527	0.008	1.118	7.161
Female	Male	-4.139*	1.527	0.008	-7.161	-1.118
Based on estimated marginal means						
*. The mean difference is significant at the .05 level.						
b. Adjustment for multiple comparisons: Least Significant Difference (equivalent to no adjustments).						

Table 6 shows the Least Significant Difference Post hoc analysis of students' performance classified by Instructional strategy. It reveals a mean difference of 4.14 and a p-value of 0.008 ($p < 0.05$) between the performance of male and female students. This indicates that the male students contributed more to the significant difference between the performance of male and female students in Radioactivity concept.

Hypothesis 3: There is no significant joint effect of instructional strategy and gender on the performance of students in Radioactivity concept.

Table 7. Summary of 2x2 Analysis of Covariance of Students' Performance Classified by Instructional Strategy and Gender Using Pretest as Covariate

Tests of Between-Subjects Effects						
Dependent Variable: Posttest						
Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared
Corrected Model	1109.302 ^a	4	277.325	5.471	0.000	0.146
Intercept	7113.790	1	7113.790	140.332	0.000	0.523
Pretest	304.798	1	304.798	6.013	0.016	0.045
Strategy	64.003	1	64.003	1.263	0.263	0.010
Gender	179.552	1	179.552	3.542	0.062	0.027
Strategy * Gender	20.678	1	20.678	0.408	0.524	0.003
Error	6488.668	128	50.693			
Total	67943.000	133				
Corrected Total	7597.970	132				
a. R Squared = 0.146 (Adjusted R Squared = 0.119)						

Table 7 reveals a value of $F_{1,128} = 1.263$, $p = 0.263$ ($p > 0.05$), partial eta squared = 0.010 for the effect of Strategy on students' performance in Radioactivity concept, a value of $F_{1,128} = 3.542$, $p = 0.062$ ($p > 0.05$), partial eta squared = 0.027 for the influence of gender on students' performance in Radioactivity concept, and a value of $F_{1,128} = 0.408$, $p = 0.524$ ($p > 0.05$), partial eta squared = 0.003 for the interaction of Strategy and gender on students' performance in Radioactivity concept. The null hypothesis is therefore retained, indicating that there is no significant joint effect of instructional

strategy and gender on students' performance in Radioactivity concept. The partial eta squared value shows that the interaction of instructional strategy and gender had a small effect on students' performance in Radioactivity concept.

Discussion

The findings of this study revealed that Interactive Simulation-based Instruction enhanced students' performance more than Video-Assisted Instruction. However, the difference in the effect of the two strategies used to teach the concept of Radioactivity was not statistically significant. Instructional strategy was found to have a small effect on students' performance in Radioactivity concept. The Interactive Simulation-based Instruction may have enhanced students' performance more than Video-Assisted Instruction because the Interactive Simulation-based Instruction provided the students, a more interactive and participatory learning experience which the Video-Assisted Instruction may not have been able to provide. Also, the difference in the effect of the two strategies used to teach the concept of Radioactivity may not have been statistically significant because the two instructional strategies are both technology based, with which the students were very familiar, being digital natives who frequently interface with digital devices. This finding agrees with the findings of Ogegbo and Ramnarain (2022) who found that Interactive Simulation Technology (IST) enhanced Grade 11 physical sciences learners' conceptual understanding of electrostatics in Physics. This finding also agrees with the findings of Ozcan et al. (2020), Arifin et al. (2022), Najib et al. (2022), and Akpan and Obafemi (2023), who found that PheT interactive simulation enhanced students' performance in scientific concepts. This finding is also in consonance with the findings of Jack and Gamnjoh (2020), Ojo (2020), Omoniyi (2021), Macaulay and Obafemi (2022), and Kaysi (2025), who found that Computer Simulation enhanced the performance of students in scientific concepts. This finding, however, contradicts the finding of Ndukwe and Obafemi (2023), who found a significant difference between the effects of guided-inquiry method and virtual laboratories, in favour of guided discovery method.

The findings of this study further revealed that the male students significantly performed better than the female students. Gender had a small effect on students' performance in Radioactivity concept. This finding may be because though science and mathematics are witnessing an improvement in the participation and performance of females who are pushing the frontiers of knowledge, there is still a wide gap in the impact of the two genders in science and mathematics. This is the situation in the study of Physics. Also, Radioactivity concept is an abstract and difficult Physics concept that requires a high level of critical thinking and mathematics ability, which are still being attributed to the male gender. This finding agrees with the finding of Obafemi and Aderonmu (2020) who discovered that the male students significantly performed better than the female students in Physics. This finding also agrees with the findings of Obafemi and Rowland (2022), Ndukwe and Obafemi (2023), and Obafemi and Ogbu (2025), who found that though the male students performed better than the female students in scientific concepts, the difference in their performance was not statistically significant. This finding however contradicts the finding of Chibabi et al. (2018), who found that the female students performed significantly higher than the male students in Biology. This finding is also at variance with the findings of Okwara et al. (2019), and Akpan and Obafemi (2023), who found that, though the female students had a higher performance than male students in Basic science and Quadratic graphs respectively, the difference in their performance was not statistically significant.

The findings of this study also revealed that the male students taught using Interactive Simulation-based Instruction had the best performance, followed by the male students taught using Video-Assisted Instruction, while the female students taught using Video-Assisted Instruction had the least performance in Radioactivity concept. The interaction of instructional strategy and gender was however not significant on the performance of students in Radioactivity concept. The interaction of instructional strategy and gender was found to have a small effect on students' performance in Radioactivity concept. This finding agrees with the findings of Ugwu and Diovu (2016), Abumchukwu et al. (2021), Macaulay and Obafemi (2022), Obafemi and Rowland (2022), Ndukwe and Obafemi (2023), and Obafemi and Ogbu (2025), who reported no significant interaction of instructional strategy and gender on students' performance in different scientific concepts. This finding however contradicts the finding of Ugwu (2014), Obafemi (2015), and Ibeneme and Akinlabi (2021) who found a significant interaction of strategy and gender on students' performance in Basic science, students' performance at the application level of students' performance in the concept of Light waves, and the performance of students in Instruction on Block laying, respectively.

Conclusion

The study investigated the effect of interactive simulation-based instruction and video-assisted instruction on students' performance in Radioactivity concept in Port Harcourt, Rivers State. The findings of the study revealed that Interactive Simulation-based Instruction enhanced students' performance more than Video-Assisted Instruction, and the male students significantly performed better than the female students. Physics is a science subject that has many difficult and abstract topics such as Radioactivity. The blending of technology-based instructional strategies such as Interactive Simulation-based Instruction and Video-Assisted Instruction with the conventional teaching methods, thus becomes necessary when teaching difficult and abstract concepts such as Radioactivity. More so, seeing that the students of this age are digital natives who find it very easy to navigate the technology world. This will go a long way to enhance the performance of the students in Physics concepts. Female students also still need all the encouragement they can get to improve their performance in Physics.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, it is recommended that:

1. Interactive Simulation-based Instruction and Video-Assisted Instruction should be employed in the teaching and learning of Physics.
2. Physics teachers should blend Interactive Simulation-based Instruction and Video-Assisted Instruction with the conventional teaching methods when teaching difficult and abstract concepts such as Radioactivity.
3. All the encouragement possible should be provided to the female students to improve their performance in Physics.

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